

Spanish Conference on Nanophotonics - CEN2021. September 20-22 2021, Vigo.

Enhanced Photoluminescence in Transition Metal Dichalcogenides Monolayers by Gold Nanoparticle Supercrystals

Joao Rodriguez⁽¹⁾, Pau Molet⁽²⁾, Leonardo Scarabelli⁽²⁾, Andrea Capasso⁽¹⁾, Agustín Mihi⁽²⁾, Pedro Alpuim⁽¹⁾, and Juan Luis Garcia-Pomar⁽¹⁾

(1) INL – International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory, Av. Mestre José Veiga, Braga, Portugal

(2) Institut de Ciència de Materials de Barcelona (ICMAB-CSIC), Campus de la UAB, 08193 Bellaterra, Spain

We developed a nanostructure to enhance the photoluminescence intensity of two-dimensional monolayers of transition metal dichalcogenides based on plasmonic supercrystal arrays. These plasmonic supercrystal arrays are deposited on top the monolayers by means of a template-assisted assembly of gold nanospheres with patterned polydimethylsiloxane molds [1]. These supercrystals arrays consist on square arrays of hexagonally packed gold nanoparticles (50 nm of diameter) which exhibit well-defined surface lattice resonance modes that can be tuned from the visible through the near-infrared by simple variation of the lattice parameter. This tunability can be used to enhance the photoluminescence emission of different transition metal dichalcogenides monolayers. So, as proof of concept, the photoluminescence signal of the monolayer MoS₂ and MoSe₂ can be significantly enhanced up to 5-6-fold coupling the frequency of the surface lattice resonance of the plasmonic supercrystal to the frequency emission of the transition metal dichalcogenides monolayer.

Figure (a) Optical image of a triangular monolayer flake of MoS₂ with an array of gold nanoparticles on top. (b) Photoluminescence map showing enhancement in the nanoparticle zone. (c),(d) Scan electron micrographies.

We greatly acknowledge financial support from the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 840064.

References:

[1] Cristiano Matricardi, Christoph Hanske, Juan Luis Garcia-Pomar, Judith Langer, Agustín Mihi, and Luis M. Liz-Marzán ACS Nano 2018 12 (8), 8531-8539